

Effect of Performance Management on Employee Performance at Teachers' Service Commission, Kenya

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Abstract: Teachers Service Commission (TSC), Kenya has been implementing performance management besides transactional rewards since 2005 to enhance quality and cost effective services. Performance management ensures performance quality improvement while transactional rewards improve efforts and productivity of employees. However, efficiency and quality of services is low compared to other state corporations as evidenced by approximately 5000 teachers who visit its head office per month to solve their work-related problems. Literatures on employee performance enhancement have focused on performance management in relation to organizational performance and employee productivity without disaggregating the same to give specific policy recommendations regarding employee performance. This study thus sought to determine the effect of performance management on employee performance at TSC, Kenya. It was anchored on Goal setting theory and adopted correlational research design. The study population was 1200 employees out of which a sample size of 291 was taken. Individual respondents were drawn through Cluster sampling technique. Primary data were collected using structured questionnaires. Pearson correlation was used to obtain association between the study variables while multiple regressions were used to establish the magnitude and direction of effect of performance management. The study revealed that performance management ($B=0.444, p=0.000$), significantly and positively predicted employee performance. This implies that performance management significantly affects employee performance. Study concludes that performance management has significant positive relationships with employee performance. Thus, TSC Kenya should affect more of it to enhance employee performance. This finding may add value to existing knowledge in employee performance enhancement strategies and human resource management policy formulations by the TSC.

Key Words: Employee performance, Performance management, Quality service, Teachers Service Commission Kenya, Transactional rewards.

1.1 Background to the Study

Like any organization, Public Sector Organizations (PSOs) are expected to fulfil the demands of the complete range of their stakeholders relevantly, efficiently, and effectively. However, since its inception in 1967, the Teachers Service Commission (TSC), Kenya has been struggling to enhance quality service in the teaching sector in Kenya. Consequently, TSC, Kenya adopted Performance management (PM) besides transactional rewards (TRs) in 2005 as the main strategy to enable it achieve its objectives for the fulfilment of the respective stakeholder demands (Okinda, 2014). PM was introduced in TSC, Kenya among the other Kenyan Public Sector Organizations (PSOs) in 2005/2006 fiscal year as part of broader Public Sector Reform Program to improve efficiency and effectiveness in the Public Service (Obong'o, 2009). PM is a continuous process of recognising, quantifying, and bettering the performance of individuals and teams, and positioning performance with the strategic goals of the organization (Aguinis, 2018). It is a means of preventing deficient performance and working together for improved performance (Bacal, 2012). For this reason, managers use it as a tool that promotes result driven cultures, accountability, and transparency due to its strong theoretical base which improves individual attitudes and eventually organizational performance (Vu, Plimmer, and Berman, 2018). Hence, it

aims at improving organizational, functional, team and individual performances (Hartog den, Bosilie and Paauwe, 2004). Ideally, PM achieves its aims through the organization's mission and strategic goals, and the task; performance arrangement; performance of duty; performance judgement; performance examination; and performance renewal and contracting (Aguinis, 2018). A well designed and implemented PM make significant contributions to employee and organizational performance (Aguinis, 2018; Chowthury, Hioe and Schaninger, 2018). The key to achieving both employee and organizational performance from PM is to implement a system that employees and managers perceive to be fair (Aguinis, 2014; 2018). To realize that perception, managers should link individuals' goals and business priorities, coach effectively and differentiate compensation across levels of performance (Chowthury, Hioe and Schaninger, 2018).

Quality and cost-effectiveness of services seems inadequate at TSC, Kenya despite the implementation of PM to improve it (TSC annual report, 2016-2017). This decrease in quality service may be attributed to lack of the best way of improving PM and its association with the repeated negative outcomes (Pulakos and O'Leary, 2011; Azzone and Palermo, 2011). Approximately, 5000 customers still visit the TSC head office monthly to sort out their work-related problems despite decentralizing the services up to sub county levels (Kauku, 2017). This is because quality performance at the TSC has been decreasing over the years as suggested by PSC reports (2006-2009, 2011 and 2012) which evaluated TSC, Kenya in terms of quality service rendered and in comparison, to other PSOs at positions 71, 94, 72, 110, 135 and 122 out of 116, 124, 130, 139, 202 and 178 PSOs in 2006 to 2009 and 2011 to 2012 respectively except in 2010 when no PSO was evaluated. From 2013 to date, no relative efficiency of the PM has been evaluated among the PSOs to determine how the TSC is performing. However, ineffective service tends to show no sign of abating (TSC, 2014). This means that from 2013 to 2021, the effect of PM on employee performance (EP) has not been ascertained at TSC, Kenya. Thus, the influence of PM on the EP at the TSC, Kenya remains unknown since 2013.

The foregoing may be blamed on the difficulties of making PM work out in many organizations since its failure rate is estimated at 56 percent globally (Hainess III and St-Onge, 2012). The difficulties arise because PM is a highly personal and often threatening process for both managers and employees (Pulakos, 2004). Thus, effectiveness of PM in enhancing EP remains doubtful. It is unclear therefore if PM's benefits have been experienced at TSC, Kenya. The 2015/2016 report on efficiency and effectiveness in service delivery reveals that the service delivery in the PSOs was either at an average or below average (PSC Report, 2016). Unless performance and productivity are emphasized in TSC, Kenya, her efforts to professionalize teaching service for quality education and development will be significantly compromised (TSC, 2019). There is therefore the need to enhance the performance of TSC, Kenya to a level that will sustain effectiveness of service delivery and productivity to enhance delivery of quality education in Kenya (Kirogo, 2019; TSC, 2019).

Studies on the relationship between PM and EP tend to approach the ways EP is influenced in diverse ways. Studies on effect of PM on EP by Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) Masome and Mangori (2017) Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) did not address the issue effectively. They were dissimilar in the aspects of focus, research designs, participants, measurements, statistics, sites, results, and conclusions. The studies of Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) Masome and Mangori (2017) Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) and Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) investigated the; PM process, weaknesses and draw backs of current PM, effectiveness of PM, influence of PMS on employee productivity, and effect of PMS on EP, respectively. The studies of Hanif Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) were qualitative while the studies of (Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia, 2019; Masome and Mangori, 2017; Said, Khan and Hameed, 2021) were quantitative. The number and type of participants in the studies of Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) and Masome and Mangori (2017) were 30, 310, 103 and 160 and of mixed cadres respectively, while the study of Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) applied seven managerial staff as the respondents. Measurements in the studies by Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) Masome and Mangori (2017) Owino Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) were all descriptive while the measurement of Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) were correlational.

Thematic interpretive analysis, content analysis, ANOVA and correlation were applied in the studies of Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) Masome and Mangori (2017) and Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) respectively and within the respective context of civil service, banking industry, referral hospitals, motor vehicle fund and airline industry. The results were thus varied. The study of Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) found PM to have certain strengths and suffering from political meddling whilst the study of Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) found that PM dissatisfies employees and that it lacks motivation and proper reward system. Knowledge of PM being positively high and being positively associated with PM effectiveness were found in the study of (Masome and Mangori, 2017). The variables of PMS having a significant and positive influence on employee productivity was

found in the study of (Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia, 2019). PM having a significant effect on EP was found in the study of (Said, Khan and Hameed, 2021).

The approaches applied in the studies are varied, dissimilar and inconsistent. The evidence somehow indicated the effectiveness of PM in organizations (Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon, 2016; Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia; 2019; Masome and Mangori, 2017; Said, Khan and Hameed, 2021) apart from one study by Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) which showed a negative result. They suffer limitations of methodologies and techniques of analysis. Their findings cannot thus be generalized in other contexts because they may raise the issues of reliability and validity. The studies therefore tend to suggest that the effectiveness of PM in organizations and EP have been examined by the researchers such as Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) Masome and Mangori (2017). However, what remains to be examined, is how it affects EP in a public teaching service sector. In this case, therefore, the researcher included PM as a predictor variable on EP and analysed its effect because the reviewed studies have overlooked that kind of relationship in a public teaching service sector.

The lack of information regarding relationship between PM and EP in a public teaching sector is limiting because they are the kind of evidence that the management, practitioners, and academicians may need if they must continue supporting EP enhancement initiatives. This study attempted to add to the pool of research knowledge in the literature available on PM with the aim of determining the relationship between PM and EP at TSC, Kenya.

1.2 Statement of the Problem

For over ten years to-date PM has become an increasingly important EP improvement strategy in TSC, Kenya. The TSC adopted the strategy besides traditional TRs to its secretariat staff in 2005 to aid in providing high customer service. The strategy should aim to provide quality service to teachers in Kenya for effective delivery of their mandates and enhance cost effective and seamless work performance, besides raising teachers' motivational level by solving their work-related problems efficiently and effectively. This requires the process of service delivery to be optimized for time efficiency, customer satisfaction, and enough clarity to be easily understood by teachers and secretariat staff. However, the current service delivery system requires continuous adjustments and promotion to make it more effective. It makes teachers lose contact hours with their learners, thus compromising quality education, and by contributing to inefficient service provision, hinders the TSC from transforming and professionalizing the teaching service for quality education and development. Monthly, the current service delivery system wastes the time of approximately 5000 teachers who visit the TSC head office to solve their work-related problems. The reports released on Performance Evaluation of Public Agencies in Kenya, and in contrast to other PSOs, rated the TSC in terms of quality service delivery at positions 71, 94, 72, 110, 135, and 122 out of 116, 124, 130, 139, 202 and 178 state corporations in 2006 to 2009 and in 2011 to 2012 respectively except in 2010 when no PSO was rated. Since 2013 to-date, the performance level of TSC, Kenya is unknown because no comparative performance analysis has been done among PSOs. These positions and assertions show that quality service at the TSC has been significantly decreasing over the past years in contrast to PM's significance in enhancing EP. Containing this problem, will practically benefit TSC, Kenya and determine the reasons for deficient performance. Literature on the reasons for, and consequences of this service; have not focused on the effect of PM on EP but on organizational performance and employee productivity and have not revealed how PM affect EP, showed inconsistent results, were conceptually and empirically fragmented, and suffers from methodological problems. TSC, Kenya employs over 306,060 teachers which require action to be taken to enable it robustly execute teacher management function. To mitigate performance deficit, the study proposed to determine the relationship between PM and EP at TSC, Kenya.

1.2 Scope of the Study

The study determined the relationship between PM and the performance of the secretariat staff at TSC, Kenya with specific reference to those deployed in the 47 Counties of Kenya. In addition, the study was restricted to the effect of PM and its key factors of setting goals and objectives, performance execution, giving and receiving coaching, and giving and receiving feedback on the performance of the secretariat staff at TSC, Kenya. The duration of the study was between 2015 and 2021.

1.3 Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.1: Conceptual Framework on the Effect of PM on Employee Performance at TSC, Kenya.

Source: Adapted from Tiraieyari and Uli (2011)

The study was guided by a conceptual framework adapted from Tiraieyari and Uli (2011) who studied the moderating effects of employee gender and organizational tenure in competency-performance relationships. From the framework, both the downward and upward arrows was eliminated and adapted one independent variable unlike the study cited which investigated two socio-demographic variables, employee gender and organizational tenure, as the moderators with social competency as the independent variable. Therefore, not all aspects of the framework were adapted from the two authors. Job performance as a dependent variable was borrowed from the framework because social competency as an independent variable was favorably associated with it. In the framework, two socio-demographic variables were used as moderators whereas in this study no moderator was applied. However, in this study only one explanatory variable, PM was applied as a proxy to social competency. This study was like the work of Tiraieyari and Uli (2011) in the sense that employee job performance is the dependent variable.

The independent variable is performance management and its key factors namely, setting goals and objectives, performance execution, giving and receiving coaching, and giving and receiving feedback. The dependent variable is the individual employee work performance whose facets include task performance, contextual performance, adaptive performance, and counter-productive work performance. Thus, it involves aligning key factors of PM to enhance employee performance. Within this framework; PM is seen as an integrated process in which managers work with the employees to set expectations, measure and review results, and reward performance to improve employee performance. The aim is to positively impact organizational success. Therefore, the effect of PM on individual employee work performance was measured and tested. It was thus, hypothesized that PM influences individual employee work performance outcomes because it involves links to organizational performance, setting individual performance goals, providing regular feedback to those goals, providing opportunities for improving and linking results and rewards.

2.0 LITRATURE REVIEW

2.1 Review of the Theory and Concepts

2.1.1 Goal - Setting Theory of Motivation

The theoretical perspective relevant to this study is the Goal Setting Theory. It was propounded by Kurt Lewin and primarily developed by Edwin Locke in 1968 as the underlying explanation for all major theories of work motivation (Newstrom, 2011). It predicts, explains, and influences employee job performance and satisfaction to trigger employee commitment in organizations (Bozkurt, Bektas, Mahir, Kola and Serra, 2017). However, its application in the service industry is very viable as the theory provides and explains causes of employee work motivation in any organization (Dessler and Varkkey, 2013). The theory indicates that a predetermined goal serves as performance enabler (Lunenburg, 2011). Thus, the most effective EP results when goals are; specific and challenging, set in a group with learning orientation, accepted by the employee, when deadlines are set for their achievement, used to evaluate performance, linked to feedback on results thereby creating commitment (Nzuve, 1999 and Lunenburg, 2011).

As the overarching theory guiding this study, goal setting theory is the most suited theory to explain PM and EP relationship. The theory enables the employee and the organization understand how the job contributes to the organization, helps the employee know what needs to be done to be successful on the job, helps the department do what needs to be done, allows the supervisor and employee identify problems early and change the course of work assignment, and enables the supervisor and employee understand that performance is an on-going process (Lunenburg, 2011). The said elements are well articulated within the constructs of PM (Aguinis, 2018). Therefore, its use in organizations for management of EP cannot be overemphasized because people can use goals as a self-management technique to ensure performance and productivity in organizations (Locke and Latham, 2002).

Furthermore, when employees know that their performance will be measured, they will meet deadlines and confront challenging situations effectively. The impact of goals will increase, typical employees will invest more effort to complete the task, and demonstrate and validate competence by seeking favourable judgements (Latham, 2011). Consequently, it is expected that employees' efforts and performance within an organization will be influenced by the goals assigned to or selected by the employees, and that successful supervisors apply the goal setting theory to clarify expectations, improve performance, and develop employees to stronger works thereby strengthening the company (Lunenburg, 2011). In addition, goal setting can function as a contract between the employee and employer thereby creating greater opportunities for accountability and growth.

2.1.2 Performance Management

Performance management (PM) is a continuous process of recognising, quantifying, and bettering the performance of individuals and teams, and positioning performance with the strategic goals of the organization (Aguinis, 2018). It deals with the challenges that organizations face in defining, measuring, and stimulating employee performance for the improvement of organizational performance (Hartog den, Bosilie and Paauwe, 2004). PM thus justifies the need for competitive advantage in organizations (Hunter, 2021). This is because it improves results in the face of challenging economic conditions among organizations that are looking into their internal capabilities for performance and productivity gains (Buchner, 2007).

Ferreira and Otley (2009) viewed PM as an aid to performing a supporting role for a broad range of managerial activities. According to Armstrong (2006), PM aims to entrench a culture of high performance among individuals and teams for which they take responsibility for the continuous improvement of business processes, their own skills, and contributions within a framework provided by effective management. Whereas Aguinis (2014) Says that PM involves a never-ending process of setting goals and objectives, observing performance, and giving and receiving ongoing coaching and feedback, and that it requires managers to ensure that employees' activities and outputs are congruent with the organization's goals. Aguinis (2018) Further posits that a never-ending process means that once PM is established in an organization, it informs an organization's culture and includes six closely related components namely prerequisites, performance planning, performance execution, performance assessment, performance review, and performance renewal and re-contracting. The PM process enables individual jobholders to: know what is expected of them in their jobs, be clear about the organizational objectives, be entitled to regular feedback on their performance, be continuously supported by their managers, and be able to continuously assess their overall performance achievement (Mwita, 2000).

Aguinis (2014) Show that PM is a much broader function of human resource management (HRM) which encompasses joint activities between employees and supervisors such as goal setting, continuous progress and frequent communication, feedback and coaching for improved performance, implementation of employees' development programme and rewarding achievement. Thus, PM is an integrating process in which managers mutually set work expectations with their employees, assess and review results to enhance employee performance (Hartog den, Bosilie and Paauwe, 2004). According to Dessler and Varkkey (2013), PM means basing your employees' training, appraisals, and rewards on fostering and rewarding the skills and competencies that the employees need to achieve their objectives. Chowthury, Hioe and Schaninger (2018) say that the principle of PM is differentiating compensation across levels of performance in addition to giving feedback and coaching.

To add value to the organization, managers, staff, and organizations should implement PM (Agarwal, 2011; Bacal, 2012) which according to Dessler and Varkkey (2013); Andrew (2009) is possible when jobs are described in terms of skills and competencies to improve corporate performance and profits as a tool for countering competition. However, according to Armstrong (2011); Werner and Desimone (2009), PM is a bundle of HRM activities designed with performance appraisal (PA) as its core activity. It also involves links to organizational performance, setting individual performance goals,

providing regular feedback to those goals, providing opportunities for improving and linking results and rewards. Consequently, PM approach requires aligning HRM practices in such a way that they maximize employee performance (Hartog den, Bosilie and Paauwe, 2004). PM that does not make explicit the employee contribution to the organizational goals is therefore not true PM (Aguinis, 2018).

At systems level, PM is more likely to promote challenging organizational assumptions that stimulate warning and emphasizes employee values and participation (Bacal, 2012). Fisher, Schoenfeldt and Shaw (2013) argue that PM is a critical factor related to an organization's long-term success in its ability to measure how well employees perform and then use that information to enable that performance meet present standards and improve over time. Aguinis (2014) Is of the opinion that performance assessment, and PA is the magnificent portion of the system level. Definite performance appraisal process, measuring performance, feedback and coaching are the principal parts of most PM.

Employers now embrace PM due to total quality, appraisal issues, and strategic planning: and increases in employee motivation and self-esteem, improved performance, clarification of job tasks and duties, clarification of supervisors' expectations, provision of self-insight and developmental opportunities to employees, provision of insight into employees' activities and goals, allowing for fairer and more appropriate administrative actions, communication of clear organizational goals, differentiation of poor and good performers, driving organizational change, encouraging voice behavior, and improving employee engagement (Dessler and Varkkey, 2013; Aguinis, 2018). In this regard, PM is seen as the most ideal model in the provision of service quality management which refers to the process of minimizing the performance gap between actual delivery and customer expectation, and it is based on the systematic use of antecedents and consequences to improve the current performance (Mwita, 2000). Different models of PM stress its importance as a system for integrating the management of organizational and EP (Hartog den, Bosilie and Paauwe, 2004). PM thus serves as an important feeder to other human resource and development activities (Aguinis, 2018).

2.1.2.1 Performance Management in the Service Sector

The service sector organizations in the economy play a significant role in any country because they contribute 50 percent of the Gross Domestic Product. They are compost of public sector organizations, hospitality, transport, education, healthcare, tourism, retail and many more (APO, 2013). They are differentiated by their own performance, services offered, and cost measurement system (Michael, 2012). Their services are highly customizable due to variation in their customers, activities, and deals (APO, 2013). Consequently, they employed thousands of employees with varied unpredictable skills, experience, and motivation (Anderson, 2006). Their efficiency and effectiveness are indicated by customer referral numbers, revenue generation, increased repeat buying, high-marks on customer feedback surveys and output (Harmon, 2006). Thus, they need to improve their productivity, and PM is the tool that can boost productivity in them. PM is compost of activities, tools and strategies for measuring and evaluating results to continuously improve (Vignieri, 2018). It also helps these organizations develop, recognize and award outstanding performers (APO, 2013). Therefore, PM aims at improving the quality of their service delivery by focusing on the achievement of end user needs (Ferreira and Otley, 2009).

2.1.2.2 Performance Management as Carried out at TSC, Kenya

Like any other PSO in Kenya, the TSC is expected to improve in performance, accountability, quality of services and value for money (Mwita, 2009). Consequently, it has been implementing PM since 2005 to get better organizational, teams and individual results by managing performance within a negotiated framework (TSC, 2018). Thus, at the Commission, the key results areas, level of performance and standards expected are identified and performance is objectively measured (TSC, 2021). The PM process at TSC, Kenya also ensures that resources are for the attainment of it's mandate (TSC, 2018). Therefore, the TSC develops strategic plan which form the basis for its performance target setting which is then cascaded to the individual level. Subsequently, the TSC Secretary enters a performance contract annually with the directors of various service areas to ensure thatTSC, Kenya achieves its set goals (TSC, 2021).

To manage and improve performance of staff, the TSC uses performance appraisal system as the core of PM by requiring all Secretariat staff to complete the prescribed appraisal form in consultation with their immediate supervisors and countersigning officers (TSC, 2018). The leadership of the service area eventually develops operational plans that deliver the desired goals. Based on the developed operational plans, the subordinates then develops work-plans derived from the one of the respective service areas (TSC, 2021). The subordinates are then assessed and rated on their performance on a quarterly basis as the directors commit to explain the variances between the actual achievement and the targets (TSC, 2021).

2.1.3 Employee Performance

Performance is what an employee does (Mathis and Jackson, 2009). It is about behavior, not what employees produce (Aguinis, 2014). Job performance is the overall expected value from employees' behavior, carried out over a set of periods of time (Motowidlo and Harrison, 2013). According to Jacobs, Hellman, Wuest and Markowitz (2020) Job performance relates to the act of doing a job and a single activity. It is also strictly behavior and a separate entity from the outcomes of the job which relate to success and productivity. EP common to all the jobs have elements such as quantity output, quality output, timeliness of output, presence at work, and cooperativeness (Mathis and Jackson, 2009).

High performance results from appropriate behavior and the effective use of the required knowledge, skills, and competitiveness (Armstrong, 2006). Performance means both behaviors and results (Brumbach, 1988). Behaviors emanate from the employee and transform performance into action and are the product of mental and physical effort applied to tasks and can be judged (Armstrong, 2009). This is because performance is evaluative (its judgement is based on whether it helps advance or hinder organizational goals) and multi-dimensional (multiple behaviors are needed to describe an employee's performance) (Aguinis, 2014). This means that there are various kinds of behavior that have the capacity to advance or hinder organizational goals (Aguinis, 2018).

In managing performance, competence factors need to be included in the process (Armstrong, 2006). This means that performance is determined by a combination of declarative knowledge (information), procedural knowledge (Know-how), and motivation (Willingness to perform) must be present for performance to reach satisfactory levels. Performance is thus a function of (declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge, and motivation) for which if any of the three determinants of performance has a small value, then performance will have an extremely low value (Aguinis, 2014; 2018). Variables inherent in the organization such as leadership, culture, work environment, motivation and training may also constrain individual EP (Hartog den, Bosilie and Paauwe, 2004). Carlson, Upton and Seaman (2006) proposed setting competitive compensation level, training and development, performance appraisal, recruitment packages, and maintenance of morale as HRM practices that positively impact EP. Whereas Tessema and Soeters (2006) concluded that the HR practices that positively and significantly associate with EP are practices that include recruitment and selection, placement, employee performance evaluation, compensation, promotion, grievance procedure, and social security. Bacal (2012) also stated that performance is affected by the interaction of the work and the individual. Important individual work performance dimensions as proposed by Koopmans et al. (2011) include task performance, contextual performance, adaptive performance, and counter-productive work behavior.

Task performance is the proficiency with which one performs central job tasks (Aguinis, 2018). Its outcomes include completing job tasks, work quantity, work quality, job skills, job knowledge, keeping knowledge up-to-date, working accurately and neatly, planning, and organizing, administration, decision making, solving problems, oral and written communication, monitoring and controlling resources (Koopmans et al, 2011). On the other hand, contextual performance refers to individual behaviors that support the organizational, social, and psychological environment in which the technical core must operate (Armstrong, 2012). The activities required to be a good member of an organization include taking on extra tasks, effort, showing initiatives, enthusiasm, attention to duty, resourcefulness, industriousness, persistence, motivation, dedication, pro-activity, creativity, cooperating with and helping others, politeness, effective communication, interpersonal relations, organizational commitment, an / or coaching new comers on the job (Aguinis, 2014; Koopmans et al, 2011).

Counter-productive work performance refers to behavior that harms the well-being of the organization. These include absenteeism, presenteeism, theft, being late to work, engaging in off-task behavior, too many or longer breaks, complaining, tardiness, doing tasks incorrectly, accidents, insulting or gossiping about co-workers, fighting, or arguing with co-workers, disregard of safety, misusing privileges, aggression, and substance abuse. Whereas adaptive performance refers to the extent to which an individual adapts to changes in a work system or work roles which include solving problems creatively, generating new and innovative ideas, adjusting goals and plans to situations, learning new tasks and technologies, being flexible and open minded to others, understanding other groups or cultures, showing resilience, remaining calm, analysing quickly, and acting appropriately (Koopmans et al, 2011; Aguinis, 2018). Performance dimensions should be included in a performance management system for organizational success (Aguinis, 2018). Logically, therefore, deficient performance is attributed to inadequate leadership, bad management, or defective systems of work, and situational and personal factors (Mwita, 2000; Armstrong, 2006).

Judging performance requires assessment using clear standards (Armstrong, 2006) which, according to Bacal (2012), has not been invented by anybody and he suggests rating, ranking and objective based as methods of performance appraisal, whereas Aguinis (2014) Suggest behavior, results, and trait approach to measure results. Moreover, Armstrong (2006) gives overall analysis of performance as written assessment, performance rating, forced distribution, quota system, and visual assessment as ways of assessing performance. Imperatively, wherever there are attempts to manage performance, a PM will be present in some form or the other (Broadbent and Laughlin, 2009). The management of performance would require that organizational and individual aims and objectives be defined and set, corporate planning be done, organizational strategy and service objectives to jobs and clients be linked, staff training and development needs be identified, results be assessed through personal appraisal while using personal indicators, performance contracts be signed, the knowledge gained through training be used to modify attitudes, external and internal communication be enhanced, and organizational development and performance review be embraced (Mwita, 2000).

2.2 Empirical Literature Review

Empirical review has advanced findings on other studies related to the influence of PM on employee performance. As recommended by Boote and Beile (2005), a substantive, thorough and systematic search was done to identify concepts related to the topic of this study. The searches were conducted between May and August, 2019 in computerized data bases such as ERIC (Educational resource information centre), EBSCO, PsycINFO, Google scholar, ProQuest, emerald and internet. The search was restricted to literature published less than 10 years and in English only. The eligibility of studies for inclusion were based on the title, abstract, concepts of employee and organizational performance, full and partial access, whereas exclusion criteria were based on: not on work performance, not at the employee level, or not at the concept of EP, and publications that had restricted retrievals. In total, the searches resulted in 20 hits from the data bases, respectively. From these, 15 were removed due to duplicity and 5 were found to be eligible on account of title and abstract. It is also worth noting that some authority provided useful guidelines and that some articles were retrieved from the internet because some are better supported by non-scholarly sources. The studies therefore provided knowledge on this topic and many of them were on developing countries. The review compared the relevant literature to identify gaps in knowledge.

2.2.1 Effect of Performance Management on Employee Performance

Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) studied performance management in public sector of Pakistan. Their purpose was to describe the performance management process in the context of Civil Service of Pakistan. The study participants were 30 composed of 28 middle, top level, and provincial management service whereas two were retired civil servants. Using qualitative research, they found PMS to be thorough, comprehensive, and disciplined tool for promotion and accountability. In addition, they also found PMS to suffer political interference, lack of qualification and standardization, and extraneous factors.

Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) conducted a qualitative study on implementation and effectiveness of performance management system (PMS) in Alfalah Bank in Pakistan. Their purpose was to identify the weaknesses and draw backs of current PM and to provide recommendations for more improvement. The population of the study was seven managerial and non-managerial employees drawn from different departments of the bank. The researchers applied interview questions and content analysis to gather and analyse data. The findings of their study show that the employees of Alfalah Bank faced the problem of dissatisfaction from their current PM and that the current PMS lacked motivation and proper reward system. They concluded that the PM of Alfalah bank lacks motivation and proper reward system. They therefore recommended direction and guidelines to improve the PMS.

Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) conducted a descriptive cross-sectional study on influence of PMS on employee productivity in county referral hospitals in Kiambu County. The variables investigated were planning, appraisal, feedback, and reward. They used proportionate stratified sampling to sample 310 respondents and SPSS version 22 to describe data and determine the extent of relationships. They found that all the four variables had a significant and positive influence on employee productivity.

Said, Khan, and Hameed (2021) studied the impact of performance management system on employee performance in Air Blue Airline in Pakistan using quantitative research method with a deductive approach survey strategy. With 160 respondents and regression and correlation, they found a significant effect of PM on EP. They therefore concluded that there was a positive meaningful relationship between PM and EP.

Masome and Mangori (2017) assessed the effectiveness of PM in a motor vehicle accident fund in a small African country. The purpose of the research was to investigate the effectiveness of the current PM approach used by motor vehicle accident fund (MVAf) and to examine the staff's knowledge level on PM and its impact on PM effectiveness. Several PMS characteristics were also analysed and their impact on PM effectiveness discussed. A quantitative approach to the research was adopted and a survey in the form of a questionnaire was used to collect data from among 103 participants among them 15, 20 and 68 were executives, senior managers, and subordinates, respectively. Their research adopted a descriptive research design to find that the knowledge of PM is high and is positively associated with PM effectiveness. They recommended that workshops dedicated to disseminating information on PM to be held every quarter.

The literature reviewed on the effect of PM on EP showed that PM is a strategy of choice for organizational, individual, and team performance improvement and that it is a tool that adds value and links people and jobs to the organizational strategy and objectives (Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon, 2016; Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia, 2019; Said, Khan and Hameed, 2021; Masome and Mangori, 2017). The studies of (Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon, 2016; Mughal, Akram, and Ali, 2014) reveal that PM does not affect employees positively. However, some reveal that PM has a positive impact on EP (Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon, 2016; Said, Khan and Hameed, 2021; Masome and Mangori, 2017; Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia, 2019). The two studies that reported on both positive and negative impact of PM used qualitative methods (Hanif, Jabin, Jadoon, 2016; Mughal, Akram, and Ali, 2014) whereas the ones which reported on positive impact and found certain strengths of PM applied quantitative research method (Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon, 2016; Said, Khan and Hameed, 2021; Masome and Mangori, 2017; Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia, 2019). The studies of Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) Masome and Mangori (2017) Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) applied 30, 310, 103 and 160 participants of various profiles, while Mughal and Akram (2014) used seven managerial staff as study participants.

The studies of Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) Masome and Mangori (2017) respectively found that PM; has certain strengths but also suffers from political meddling, dissatisfies employees, and lacks motivation and proper reward system, and that the knowledge of PM among employees was high and positively associated with its effectiveness. Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) found PM to have an impact on employee productivity, and the study of Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) found a significant effect of PM on EP. The studies were conducted in different contexts: Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) did their study within civil service of Pakistan; whilst the study of Mughal, Akram and Ali (2014) was done within the banking industry; whereas the study of (Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia, 2019) was conducted in county referral hospitals; Masome and Mangori (2017) performed their research in a motor vehicle fund organization; and however, Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) conducted their research in an airline industry. Mixed cadres of employees as participants were in the researches on effect of PM on EP (Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon, 2016; Masome and Mangori, 2017; Said, Khan and Hameed, 2021). The exception was with the study of (Mughal, Akram, and Ali, 2014) which involved managers. The studies of Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) Masome and Mangori (2017) and Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) applied 30, 7, 310 and 160 in their researches as the sample size, respectively. The studies of Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon (2016) Mughal, Akram, and Ali (2014) are similar in relation to research designs. All applied qualitative research designs. However, Masome and Mangori (2017) Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) and Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) designed their study using quantitative designs.

The researchers are dissimilar in their studies in terms of research designs, sample sizes, profile of participants and results (Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon, 2016; Mughal, Akram, and Ali, 2014; Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia, 2019; Masome and Mangori, 2017; Said, Khan and Hameed, 2021). The authors (Hanif, Jabin and Jadoon, 2016; Mughal, Akram, and Ali, 2014; Masome and Mangori, 2017) focused the study of PM on organizational performance other than employee performance and Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia (2019) focused their study on employee productivity and Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) focused their study on EP.

The writers on effect of PM on EP have varied focus, designs, profile and number of participants, and contexts of their studies as compared to this study. Their studies did not focus on EP, but on organizational performance and employee productivity. The exception is with the studies of (Owino, Oluoch and Kimemia, 2019; Masome and Mangori, 2017; Said, Khan and Hameed, 2021) who applied quantitative methods. However, a significant similarity to this study is with the study of Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) who studied the effect of PM on EP with quantitative research design. The differences in methodologies, nature, and sample sizes, focus and contexts of studies, and differences in results have made the findings of the studies ambiguous and inconsistent. These researchers tried to find out the impact that PM

would have on organizational and employee productivity. However, they did not study PM in relation to EP. Therefore, this study sought to determine the effect of PM on EP at TSC, Kenya.

3.0 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

3.1 Research Design

The study is quantitative and thus employed correlational research design since it allows by inquiry to establish the effect of PM on EP at TSC, Kenya (Creswell, 2014).

3.2 Study Area

The study was conducted in the TSC, Kenya offices in 47 Counties and more than 230 Sub-County TSC administrative units in Kenya. The choice of TSC, Kenya as the context of the study was guided by the fact that it is not the only single largest employer among the Public Sector Employers in Kenya, but also in East and Central Africa, and the choice of counties were informed by the fact that they have provided services closer to the people through decentralization of the TSC functions and improved teacher supervision at the institutional level (TSC Annual Report, 2016-2017). Article 251 (1) (c) of the Kenyan Constitution allows the TSC to recruit its own professional, technical, and administrative staff to form the secretariat as per section (18) (1) of the TSC Act 2012 Laws of Kenya. Consequently, it has employed over 3000 secretariat employees apart from the commissioners of whom about 1200 are stationed in the field to enable it discharge its mandates (TSC, 2017).

Kenya is delineated by coordinates between the latitudes 0.0236'S and longitudes 37.9062'E and it is inhabited by 44 communities. It is bordered by Tanzania to the south, Uganda to the south-west, South Sudan to the north-west, Ethiopia to the north, Somalia to the north-east and on the south-east by the Indian Ocean. Located in eastern coast of Africa and lies a stride of the equator and on the west of Lake Victoria. Kenya's total land boundary length is 3477 km and coast line of 536 km with the total area, including 11230 km² of water, 582650 km² of land, and a maximum length of 1131 km SSE-NNW and a maximum width of 1025 km ENE-WSW. The Population and Housing Census of 2019 reveal that Kenya is inhabited by 47.6 million persons with an annual growth rate of 2.2 percent. There is a total of 31,661 public primary and post primary educational institutions across the country which is served by 306,060 teachers with a total enrolment approximated at 12,282,904 learners.

3.3 Target Population

The Population of the study was the current 1200 TSC, Kenya secretariat staff stationed in all counties of Kenya from which the study sample was identified. The county staffs are comparable to the head office staff in terms of gender, age, educational level, professional qualification and experience, and job roles. They were chosen because counties have strengthened the decentralization of TSC functions and improved teacher supervision at the institutional level.

3.4 Sampling Techniques and Sample Size

Cluster sampling technique was used to select the study respondents because they were scattered in their respective 47 counties and 230 sub counties in Kenya. Therefore, it was not possible to obtain a sampling frame from them as supported by Mugenda (2008). A sample size of 291 secretariat staff was determined using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sample size estimation Table although 296 of them participated in the study.

3.5 Sources and Types of Data

Sources of data were the TSC secretariat employees deployed in the counties of Kenya. The dependent variable, EP was ratio scaled. Own designed questionnaires were used to collect quantitative primary data.

3.6 Pretesting of Research Instrument

Piloting was conducted in Migori County on 10th February, 2021. The piloted county was selected through simple random sampling technique. The number of participants to be piloted in a study is debatable. Mugenda (2008) propose the number to be piloted to be between 1% and 10% depending on the sample size. On the other hand, Sudman (1983) recommends 12 to 50 people because the number is cost, energy, and time efficient which is a large enough number that will note the problems with the survey questions. Therefore, to increase the likelihood of success of this study, the instrument was pilot tested on a small group of 21 respondents who were like the intended participants and within the range of the recommendations of (Sudman, 1983; Mugenda, 2008). Furthermore, 21 participants are adequate for piloting because, according to Hertzog (2008), samples in the size range typical of pilot studies produce imprecise and sometimes seriously biased estimates of relevant statistics.

The sampled County had 21 TSC secretariats of the 1200 study population, and the 21 secretariats were all piloted. The piloted population was a representative sample for piloting because the number was cost, energy, and time efficient to note the problems with survey questions (Sudman, 1983). The aim of pilot test was to determine the validity and reliability of the research instrument as per the study objectives. Piloting ensured that the entire survey schedule ran smoothly and that coding and analyses were done properly and efficiently. The pilot test was also done to establish whether; there was question item flow and other areas for improvement, the instructions to respondents were clear, and the objectives of the study were being effectively addressed before the actual data collection process. The pilot county was excluded in the main study. The research instrument which was piloted was the researcher's own developed questionnaires. Generally: the findings for piloting study indicated that the items in the instruments were very clear, understood well by the respondents, and the content was relevant and valid to the study, however the respondents suggested revision on HR technical terminologies to every day English language terms; the maximum time taken to administer the questionnaire was 15 minutes and the respondents had no issue with the length of the questionnaires; and the researcher was well received in the pilot county which could be attributed to the earlier communication to them by TSC over the upcoming research. The pilot results determined that content in the questionnaire is valid and relevant for collection of data for this research.

3.7 Reliability and Validity Testing

Reliability measures the degree to which the research instrument yields consistent results after repeated trials (Mugenda, 2008). To minimize random error, a reliability coefficient of 0.933 and 0.720 for PM and EP respectively were computed. These against the threshold of Cronbach's Coefficient set at $\alpha = .7$, suggest that the instrument used was reliable (Mugenda, 2008; Creswell, 2014). The study applied construct validity to measure the theoretical concepts of TRs and EP (Mugenda, 2008; Aila and Ombok, 2015). The results showed that the instrument was highly valid and yields data that has construct validity, allowing 8-10% non-random error.

3.8 Measurement of Variables

PM and EP were measured on an instrument as a continuous score and the scores from the sample were expected to be normally distributed. Ordinary least square (OLS) techniques were used to estimate various parameters associated with PM and EP. The result of multiple regressions being conducted at 95% level of significance was compared with the result of OLS to determine the significance of performance estimated. Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis was undertaken to establish the magnitude and direction of the association between PM and EP (Mutai, 2014; Creswell, 2014). The outcome was therefore presented in form of tables and textual write-ups because they enable readers refine and distil the data to glean relevant information (Mutai, 2014).

3.9 Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, correlation and regression analysis were used to analyse data. Descriptive statistics enables the researcher to discover miscoded values, missing data, and other problems in data set (Mutai, 2014). It also enables the researcher to organize, summarize, interpret, and communicate quantitative information obtained from the study (Hayes, 2021). Pearson Product-Moment Correlation analysis was conducted to determine the magnitude and direction of the relationship between PM and EP at TSC, Kenya (Aguinis, 1995). Multiple regression analysis is an accessible data analytic technique in major statistical packages (Frazier, Baron, and Tix, 2004). A typical simple regression model is of the form;

$$EP = f(PM) \dots\dots\dots (3.1)$$

However, the several explanatory variables within PM are setting goals and objectives (SGO), performance execution (PE), giving and receiving coaching (GRC), and giving and receiving feedback (GRF)..... (3.2)

The regression model and corresponding general function representing EP as adapted from (Mukras, 2012; Mutai, 2014) and modified by the researcher are as follows:

$$EP = f(PM) = (SGO, PE, GRC, GRF) \dots\dots\dots (3.3)$$

Thus, the mathematical form of the multiple regression model is expressed as:

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1SGO_i + \beta_2PE_i + \beta_3GRC_i + \beta_4GRF_i \dots\dots\dots (3.4)$$

The equation (3.4) Can be re-specified after incorporating the disturbance term as:

$$EP_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1SGO_i + \beta_2PE_i + \beta_3GRC_i + \beta_4GRF_i + \epsilon_i \dots\dots\dots (3.5)$$

Where: EP_i is the employee performance; i , individual employee; SGO , setting goals and objectives; PE , performance execution; GRC , giving and receiving coaching; GRF , giving and receiving feedback; ϵ , error term; β_0 the intercept; and $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3$ and β_4 are the slopes of the variables SGO_i, PE_i, GRC_i and GRF_i , respectively.

4.0 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

4.1 Results of the Study

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

According to Trochim (2020), descriptive statistics describe the basic features of data, provide summaries about the sample and the measures, and form the basis of every quantitative analysis of data in a study. Its purpose is to simplify and organize a set of scores (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2004). They are however, a straightforward way of describing the collected data, but do not allow the making of conclusions beyond the analysed data or reach conclusions on hypotheses that might have been made (Babbie, 2010).

4.1.2 Summary of the Descriptive Statistics

Table 4.1: Summary of Descriptive Statistics

	Descriptive Statistics							
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Variance	Skewness	Kurtosis		
	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Statistic	Std. Error	Std. Error	
Performance Management	296	3.67	.683	.466	-.757	.142	1.272	.282
Employee Performance	296	3.38	.587	.344	-.125	.142	.171	.282
Valid N (listwise)	296							

Source: Field data, 2021

The mean is the average of a set of scores or measurements (Mugenda, 2008). It is obtained by adding up the scores and dividing by the number of observations (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2004). A five-point Likert scale was used to measure PM and EP. This is a psychometric response scale in which the study responders to research questions specified their level of agreement to a statement in five points- strongly disagree, disagree, neither agree nor disagree, agree, and strongly agree (Preedy & Watson, 2010). Table 4.1 indicates that the respondents neither agreed nor disagreed with EP (M= 3.38) while they agreed with PM (M=3.67). This means that the knowledge of PM is high and is positively associated with its effectiveness at TSC, Kenya (Masome & Mangori, 2017).

There was a need to know how scores differed among themselves in magnitude around the mean of the distribution (Mutai, 2014). This is because samples consistently tend to be less variable than their populations, giving a biased estimate of population variability (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2004). Therefore, standard deviation was applied because it gives the extent to which scores in a distribution deviate from their mean (Mugenda, 2008). The scores in PM (SD=.683) and EP (SD=.587) are clustered close together and variability is small. This shows that the individual responses on average are a little less than 1 point from the mean, meaning respondents respectively neither agreed nor disagreed with EP and PM. This implies that TSC, Kenya may have not prioritized the achievement of its goals to employees' performance.

The distributions in this study are negatively skewed. Skewness is a measure of horizontal departure from distribution (Mugenda, 2008). Negative skewness implies that most of the measures are remarkably high with very few low measures and the values are less than -1.0 (Gravetter & Wallnau, 2004). This means that the scores have piled up to the right-hand side and the tail tapered off to the left (Jushan & Serena, 2005). Thus, PM and EP are negatively skewed as indicated by the values -.757 and -.125 respectively. Hence, mass of the distribution is concentrated on the left, with PM being the most negatively skewed. Therefore, it can be concluded that the distribution is normal.

Kurtosis is a measure of vertical departure from normal distribution (Jushan & Serena, 2005; Mugenda, 2008). In a normal distribution, kurtosis will always be equal to 3 and a departure from it shows either a peaked (leptokurtic) or a flat (platykurtic) distribution (Jushan & Serena, 2005). All variables were flat (platykurtic) 1.27 and .17 for PM and EP, respectively. This implies that their standard deviation from the mean is not outside the range of normality. Standard errors for skewness and kurtosis are all the same for PM and EP at .142 and .282 for skewness and kurtosis, respectively. They reflect the functions of the sample size.

4.2 Correlation Analysis

Correlation analysis was carried out to measure the degree of relationship between the variables and the results are indicated in Table 4.2. The results in Table 4.2 show the association between performance management and employee performance at TSC, Kenya.

Table 4.2: Association between Performance Management and Employee Performance at TSC, Kenya

		Totals for employee's performance	Totals for performance management
Totals for employee performance	Pearson correlation Sig.(2-tailed) N	296	
Totals for performance management	Pearson correlation Sig. (2-tailed) N	.517 .000** 296	1 296

**** . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed)**

Source: Field data, 2021

Table 4.2 show that PM ($r=0.517$, $p=0.000$), has moderate significant positive association with EP at TSC, Kenya. This means that 51.7% in EP at TSC, Kenya can be significantly associated with PM, although the existence of association between two or more variables does not necessarily imply any causal relationship (Mukras, 2012; Curwin & Slater, 2013). The findings suggest a possibility of a positive relationship between, PM and EP at TSC, Kenya.

The respective influences of the constructs of PM on EP at TSC, Kenya were isolated for further correlation analysis and the results are shown in Table 4.3.

Table 4.3: Association between the Constructs of Performance Management and Employee Performance at TSC, Kenya

Correlations.		Setting goals and objectives	Giving and receiving feedback	Giving and receiving coaching	Performance execution	Total employee performance
Setting goals and objectives	Pearson Correlation Sig.(2-tailed) N	1 296				
Giving and receiving feedback	Pearson Correlation Sig.(2-tailed) N	.721 .000** 296	1 296			
Giving and receiving coaching	Pearson Correlation Sig.(2-tailed) N	.551 .000** 296	.710 .000** 296	1 296		
Performance execution	Pearson Correlation Sig.(2-tailed) N	.554 .000** 296	.578 .000** 296	.409 .000** 296	1 296	
Total employee performance	Pearson Correlation Sig.(2-tailed) N	.557 .000** 296	.617 .000** 296	.538 .000** 296	.589 .000** 296	1 296

**** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).**

Source: Field data, 2021.

The constructs that form PM are setting goals and objectives, giving, and receiving feedback, giving, and receiving coaching and performance execution. The results indicating the extent to which each construct is related to EP and to what extent the variation in each of them changes with the variation in EP at TSC, Kenya are shown in Table 4.3. Setting goals and objectives ($r=0.557$, $p=0.000$), giving and receiving feedback ($r=0.617$, $p=0.000$), giving and receiving coaching ($r=0.538$, $p=0.000$) and performance execution ($r=0.589$, $p=0.000$), all had moderate significant positive association with employee performance at TSC, Kenya. This means that 55.7%, 61.7%, 53.8% and 58.9% in EP at TSC, Kenya can be significantly associated with setting goals and objectives, giving, and receiving feedback, giving, and receiving coaching and performance execution respectively, although the existence of association between two or more variables does not necessarily imply any causal relationship (Mukras, 2012; Curwin & Slater, 2013). The findings suggest a possibility of a positive relationship between setting goals and objectives, giving and receiving feedback, giving, and receiving coaching, performance execution and EP at TSC, Kenya.

4.3Regression Analysis

Multiple linear regression analysis was carried out to establish the effect of PM on EP at TSC, Kenya and results are indicated in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Regression Coefficients of Performance Management

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.749	.160		10.921	.000		
Performance management	.444	.043	.517	10.346	.000**	1.000	1.000

- a. Dependent Variable: Average Employee Performance
- b. **. Indicates statistical significance level at 5% level (2-tailed)

Source: Field data, 2021

Table 4.4 show that PM ($B=0.444$, $P=0.000$) is a significant positive predictor of EP at TSC, Kenya. The t-statistic of 10.35 against a p-value of 0.000 suggests that the coefficient of PM is significant. This implies that for every unit change in PM, the EP at TSC, Kenya changes by 0.444 units. Therefore, the null hypothesis that PM has no significant effect on EP at TSC, Kenya is rejected. The standard error which is a measure of uncertainty about the true value of the regression (PM) coefficient is 4.3%. The variance of inflation factor for PM is 1, is within the threshold of 4 recommended by Pan and Jackson (2008) shows that there is no multicollinearity. The regression model equation for this relationship is: $EP = 1.749 + 0.444PM \dots \dots \dots (4.1)$.

$$SE: (0.160) (0.043)$$

$$t: (10.921) (10.346)$$

Although the focus of this study was the analysis of the effect of PM on EP at TSC, Kenya, analysis on the effects of the constructs that formed PM was also done. The findings of this analysis are respectively shown in Table 4.5.

Table 4.5: Regression Coefficients for the Indicators of Performance Management

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	T	Sig.	Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	1.385	.171		8.088	.000**		
Performance Execution	.180	.046	.234	3.880	.000**	.624	1.603
Setting Goals and Objectives	.154	.049	.214	3.156	.002**	.493	2.028
Giving and Receiving Coaching	.063	.043	.091	1.463	.145	.583	1.715
Giving and Receiving Feedback	.129	.051	.168	2.532	.012**	.518	1.929

- c. Dependent Variable: Average Employee Performance
- d. **. Indicates statistical significance level at 5% level (2-tailed)

Source: Field data, 2021

Table 4.5 shows that there is a significant positive relationship between the constructs that formed performance management namely -performance execution ($B_2=0.180$, $p=0.000$), setting goals and objectives ($B_1=0.154$, $p=0.002$) giving

and receiving feedback ($B_4=0.129$, $p=0.012$) and EP at TSC, Kenya. This implies that for every unit change in performance execution, setting goals and objectives and giving and receiving feedback, the EP at TSC, Kenya changes by 0.180, 0.154 and 0.129 units, respectively. However, giving and receiving coaching ($B_3=0.063$, $p=0.145$) as a construct that also formed PM, has insignificant positive influence on EP at TSC, Kenya. This means that as at the time of conducting this research, the programme for coaching might have not been initiated at TSC, Kenya alternatively, the supervisors may not be implementing PM effectively. Table 4.5 further indicate that performance execution ($\beta_2=0.234$, $p=0.000$) has the strongest effect on EP at TSC, Kenya. The variance of inflation factors for the independent factors ranges between 1.603 and 2.028, which meet the threshold of 4 recommended by Pan and Jackson (2008) attests that there is no multicollinearity. The regression model equation for this relationship is:

$$EP = 1.385 + 0.154SGO + 0.180PE + 0.063GRC + 0.129GRF \dots\dots\dots (4.2).$$

SE: (0.171) (0.046) (0.049) (0.043) (0.051)

t: (8.088) (3.880) (3.156) (1.463) (2.532)

The findings of this study compares with the past studies. According to Armstrong (2006), to stimulate employee performance for the enhancement of organizational performance, is to entrench a culture of high performance among individuals and teams within a framework provided by effective management. Most of the impetus to the entrenchment of a culture of employee high performance falls within the ambit of PM. Thus, this study finding concurs with the study of Said, Khan and Hameed (2021) and Masome & Mangori (2017), which studied the impact of PMS in an airline company in Pakistan and in a motor vehicle accident fund in a small African country, and found a positive association between employee performance, organizational effectiveness, and PM, respectively. This is because employee contributions to the organizational goals are clearly explained.

Surprisingly, Hanif, Jabin & Jadoon (2016), who studied PM in the public sector of Pakistan, found certain strength of PM, and to be suffering from political interference, lack of qualification and standardization, and extraneous factors that hinder its effective functioning. Whereas, Owino, Oluoch & Kimemia (2019) explored the influence of PMS on employee productivity in County referral hospitals of Kiambu County in Kenya finds a significant and positive influence of PMS on employee productivity. These results may be attributed to having regular review and discussions with employees and provision of regular constructive feedback. Contrastingly, Mughal, Akram & Ali (2014) studied the scope of PM effectiveness in Alfalah Bank in Pakistan finds dissatisfaction with the current PM and that it lacks motivation and proper reward system. The likely reason for this result is that the PM system in this institution may have not been professionally designed and implemented and not working as intended. Past studies tried to determine the effectiveness of PM in organizations. However, the effect of PM on EP had not been investigated. Therefore, the relation between PM and EP was still unknown. This study determined the relation between PM and EP at TSC, Kenya and the results indicate that a unit increase in PM results in an increase of 0.444 units in EP at TSC, Kenya. The result from this study has shown that PM is not only effective in organizations as shown in the past studies, but also on EP. The significance of the finding of this study is that it has informed an understanding of how PM influences EP thus, enhance the theory of the relationship between PM and EP.

The residual diagnostics was carried out and the results are captured in Table 4.6. The residuals of the transformed data when plotted indicate that they are normally distributed with a mean of zero when the histogram is a bell shaped (Nikhil, Kingshuk & Mihir, 2015).

Table 4.6: Residual Statistics for the Effect of PM on EP

	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation	N
Predicted Value	2.19	3.97	3.38	.303	296
Residual	-1.193	1.363	.000	.503	296
Std. Predicted Value	-3.908	1.949	.000	1.000	296
Std. Residual	-2.370	2.707	.000	.998	296

Source: Field data, 2021

The result in Table 4.6 indicates that the bell-shape of the histogram was realized because the residuals are distributed around their mean. It is noted that residuals are identically distributed with mean being at zero and at equal variance, therefore it can be concluded that the model had met the assumption of homoskedasticity.

5.0 CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study was to establish the effect of PM on the performance of employees at TSC, Kenya. Results indicate significant positive effect of PM on EP at TSC, Kenya. The PM indicator of performance executions reported highest significant positive effect on EP, followed by setting goals and objectives, giving, and receiving feedbacks, and giving, and receiving coaching. This implies that of the PM indicators, performance execution and setting goals and objectives were highly regarded in influence to EP improvement in comparison to giving and receiving feedback, and giving and receiving coaching at TSC, Kenya. It is therefore recommended that to enhance EP at the TSC Kenya, there is need to emphasise more on performance execution and setting goals and objectives. In addition, giving and receiving feedback, and giving and receiving coaching also play a significant role on EP.

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